

1 Major immunologic effectors produced following Plasmodium infection.

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3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 We report that in the peripheral blood, humans infected with Plasmodium produced high levels of IL-10.
7 We also observed induction of the receptor for IL-31, *IL31RA* in humans in the whole blood during active,
8 symptomatic Malarial infection caused by *P. falciparum*. Akin to skewing of Th1/Th2 lineage responses by
9 helminth infections, Plasmodium falciparum infection here was associated with induction of a strong
10 toleragenic response defined by IL-10.

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